

Why should you invest in the office sector?

In the recent few years, office buildings have been in high demand. This leads us to the following question, with the rate of construction, is it still profitable to invest in this segment?

Asher Roshanzamir, [CEO of Zamir Equities](#), indicates that the positive trend has been sustained by economic stability, low inflation and sustained internal growth.

To meet the high level of demand of the main national and foreign companies, an offer of corporate spaces with the quality, efficiency, technology and security at the height of the best projects in the world is required.

The greatest demand for spaces comes from users of professional services, financial services, automotive, energy and telecommunications.

“We are especially optimistic about the eventual but imminent integration and growth of new and important players in the energy sector,” says [Asher Roshanzamir](#).

Additionally, the great demand of public sector entities prevails, which require efficient, dignified and functional real estate spaces.

Today the expectation of the return on investment in dollars of investors in the lease of new class A + and A spaces is in the range of 7 to 10% depending on the term of the contract, credit quality of the tenant and scale of the requirement; meanwhile, in the segment of class B spaces, the expected range is 8-12 percent.

“We consider that an excellent strategy to maximize success in office projects is in the integration of mixed-use real estate concepts,” says Asher Roshanzamir.

[Investments in the office sector](#) have been attractive, solid, profitable and with great capital gains in the long term; However, under the current market circumstances, there are great risks if there is not an adequate real estate consultancy that considers direct and indirect competition in each case, since it is essential to specifically analyze the commercial strategy (sale or rent), the demand in the area (minimum square meters to be offered), the price (starting, closing and volume discounts), as well as the time and conditions of the lease and / or sale.